

ESTIMATION ADVANTAGES OF ENDOSCOPY IN DIAGNOSTICS OF CHRONIC EXUDATIVE OTITIS MEDIA

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The number of patients with hearing impairments is growing steadily. In 2002, there were about 240 million people in the world with hearing impairments, by 2030, the World Health Organization predicts an increase in the number of people with socially significant hearing impairments by more than 30% [1,4,5]. In the general problem of chronic otitis media, the problem of chronic catarrhal inflammation of the mucous membrane of the middle ear now comes out on top [2,3].

The aim of this study was to conduct an endoscopic analysis of the state of the structures of the nasopharynx in children with exudative otitis media.

Research material. The work is based on the results of clinical observations and treatment of 56 children with exudative otitis media aged from 3 to 18 years for the period from 2016 to 2020. In the Bukhara Regional Children's Multidisciplinary Center, the clinical examination of children included: clarifying complaints, taking anamnesis, conducting rhinoscopy, pharyngoscopy, otoscopy (including video otoscopy and endoscopy), lateral projection of the nasopharynx x-ray, endoscopic examination of the nasal cavity and nasopharynx using rigid and flexible optical systems, if necessary, an X-ray examination of the paranasal sinuses and temporal bones was carried out according to the methods of Schüller and Mayer to determine the degree of pneumatization of the mastoid process of the temporal bone.

Results and its discussion. In the period from 2016 to 2020, 56 patients aged 3 to 14 years with exudative otitis media were examined. Unilateral exudative otitis media was observed in 18 patients (32.2%), the diagnosis of bilateral exudative otitis media was made in 38 patients (67.8%). Thus, exudative otitis media most often had a two-sided nature of the course and was twice as common in patients as a one-sided process.

Diagnosis of exudative otitis media included otoscopy (including endoscopy), in which the color, transparency, retraction or bulging of the tympanic membrane, position and severity of its identification contours were assessed; the presence or absence of exudate behind the eardrum with the level of fluid, scars; the presence of retraction pockets, endoscopic examination of the nasal cavity and nasopharynx, which made it possible to assess in detail the condition of the nasal mucosa, turbinates, nasal septum; examine the lymphoid structures of the nasopharynx, establish their exact location relative to each other, visually assess the state of the elements of the pharyngeal opening of the auditory tube when performing functional tests of Toynbee and Valsalva, observe the process of catheterization and blowing the auditory tubes, when assessing the dysfunction of the pharyngeal opening of the auditory tube, we used the working classification proposed, which identifies 3 main types of dysfunction of the pharyngeal orifice of the auditory tube: 1) obstructive, 2) reflux - dysfunction, 3) gapping

auditory tube, tone threshold audiometry and acoustic impedance measurement with determination of the function of the auditory tube.

It should be noted that for the first time we, on the basis of complaints, anamnesis and examination, revealed exudative otitis media in 27 children (48%). The study of auditory function and treatment of this group of patients were not carried out before contacting us. In 21 patients (37%) admitted to our clinic, the diagnosis of chronic exudative otitis media was not made for the first time, which confirms the persistent course of the disease for a long time and the low level of effectiveness of the methods of conservative or previously performed surgical treatment of exudative otitis media. During our examination, all these children had conductive hearing loss of I-II degrees during the course of tonal threshold audiometry; when performing acoustic impedance measurements, the tympanogram type "B" or "C" was determined. The auditory function also did not recover in 21 patients after adenotomy. In addition, 8 patients (19%) had previously undergone tympanic shunting with the installation of Teflon and ceramic shunts, but after removal of the ventilation tube and closure of the perforation hole during audiological examination, persistent conductive hearing loss of the 1st degree remained.

Complaints of older children were about hearing loss, noise of various nature and a feeling of stuffiness in the ears. Parents of patients in the younger age group also noted hearing loss, complained about the child's inattention, and frequent questioning. From the anamnesis it was found that children often suffered from acute medium catarrhal and purulent otitis media, which had a tendency to protracted or recurrent course, acute adenoiditis, rhinosinusitis. The main otoscopic sign in all age groups was the determination of the exudate behind the tympanic membrane, as well as retraction of the tympanic membrane, indicating a decrease in pressure in the tympanic cavity, smoothing of its contours, color change and deformation of the light reflex. In children with cicatricial processes in the region of the pharyngeal opening of the auditory tube, retraction pockets of the tympanic membrane were more often determined. With an abundant amount of exudate in the tympanic cavity, a swelling of the tympanic membrane was noted. Simultaneous endoscopy and blowing of the auditory tubes according to Politzer with transnasal endoscopic control made it possible to diagnose cicatricial changes in the tympanic membrane, revealing the limitation of its mobility; this indicated adhesive phenomena in the tympanic cavity. Audiometric indices revealed hearing loss in all patients examined by us.

When conducting tonal threshold audiometry, the largest number of children with conductive hearing loss of I-II degrees was found in the age group from 3 to 7 years. Grade III conductive hearing loss was detected much less frequently, and the predominant age of children was from 7 to 12 years.

The study of the auditory function by the method of acoustic impedance measurement made it possible to determine the presence of exudate in the tympanic cavity. When performing acoustic impedance measurements in the majority of children (50 ears), tympanograms corresponded to type "C" (46%). At the age of 3 to 7 years, the prevailing number of children were with type B tympanograms (6 ears). If we trace the age composition of patients, then the number of pathological tympanograms decreases with age, but the type of tympanograms "B" (22.8%) and "C" without an acoustic reflex (23%) in the age group from 12 to 14 years old

remains quite stable, despite for ongoing conservative treatment. In the course of our examination, it was found that 92 ears (38%) corresponded to type B tympanogram, 74 ears (31%) - type C tympanogram without an acoustic reflex, 36 ears (15%) - type C tympanogram with acoustic reflex and 38 ears (16%) - corresponded to the norm, type "A".

All 120 patients underwent a study of the function of the auditory tube. Lack of patency of the auditory tube was found in all patients with type B tympanograms (60 people) and in 20 patients with type C tympanograms without recording an acoustic reflex.

According to endoscopic examination of the nasopharynx, only 7 patients (8%) aged 12 to 14 years had grade I adenoids. During visual examination of the nasopharynx, the most common types of obstruction of the pharyngeal orifices of the auditory tubes with adenoid vegetations of the II degree were found in 26 (29%) of 42 children (47%), aged 3 to 13 years. And in 16 people (18%) grade II adenoids had predominantly horizontal growth, did not cover the mouths of the auditory tubes, but fit tightly to the tubal ridges. Hypertrophy of the tubal rolls was found in 7 children. Grade III adenoid vegetations were observed in 40 patients (45%) aged 3 to 12 years, while in 33 people (37%), they took part in the obstruction of the pharyngeal opening of the auditory tube. In addition, they penetrated into the choanae, occupying 1/3 of the posterior parts of the nasal cavity. In 4 children (5%) out of 40 (45%), the adenoids moved to the choanas only when swallowing, which coincided with the opening of the auditory tube, blocking the flow of air into it at that moment. In 3 (3%) of 40 patients (45%) grade III adenoid vegetations were mixed vertically without affecting the auditory tube. At the age of 12 to 14 years, we detected, as a rule, a slight increase in adenoid vegetation, and in some cases their presence was associated with a relapse of the disease. Endoscopic examination of the nasopharynx made it possible to correlate the size of the pharyngeal tonsil and distribute patients of different age groups according to the degree of adenoid hypertrophy.

In children with exudative otitis media, obstructive dysfunction of the auditory tube predominated according to the proposed working classification. According to the results of endoscopic examination of the nasopharynx in children with grade I-II adenoid vegetations, horizontal growth of the pharyngeal tonsil prevails, overlapping the pharyngeal orifices of the auditory tubes.

Nasal breathing in such patients is slightly difficult. In children, grade II-III adenoids occupy almost the entire volume of the nasopharynx, cover the pharyngeal orifices of the auditory tubes, prolapse into the posterior parts of the nose, thereby significantly complicating nasal breathing. On the basis of a carefully collected anamnesis and data of endoscopic examination of the nasal cavity and nasopharynx in the group of children studied by us, the main role in the block of the pharyngeal opening of the auditory tube in exudative otitis media at the age of 3 to 12 years is played by adenoid vegetations, hypertrophy of the tubal tonsils and tubal ridges, the course of acute and chronic adenoiditis, as well as postponed acute otitis media. In children aged 12 to 14 years, the main etiological factors in the development of exudative otitis media were often acute rhinosinusitis and curvature of the nasal septum, which led to a violation of the viscosity of the secretion, changed the movement of mucus in the nose, creating prerequisites for the reflux of secretions into the pharyngeal orifices of the auditory tubes. According to our data, the cause of exudative otitis media can also be cicatricial changes in the

region of the pharyngeal opening of the auditory tube, a significant number of which occur at the age of 7 to 12 years (12 children), this group of patients has repeatedly undergone adenotomy without endoscopic control, has not been performed allergological examination.

Thus, it follows that, on the one hand, diseases of the nasal cavity, paranasal sinuses, otitis media, allergic background in 26.7% of children, and on the other hand, anatomical and functional changes in the structures of the nasopharynx led to disturbances in the ventilation, drainage and evacuation functions of the auditory tubes, contributing to the development of exudative otitis media. Endoscopic examination is an additional research method in the diagnosis of EOM.

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